

Engine room of the future – lessons learned in the development of MARIN's Zero Emission Laboratory

Menno Merts¹, Jan de Boer¹, Jeroen Willemsen¹, Hans Bruisten¹, Udai Shipurkar¹, Bart-Jan Sustronk¹ and Moritz Krijgsman¹

¹ MARIN, Wageningen, The Netherlands

Abstract. The biggest challenge the maritime sector is currently facing, is the implementation of technologies to achieve its greenhouse gas reduction goals. Doing this for the complete field of maritime applications involves a wide range of technologies and energy-carriers. Besides suitable for the ships mission, the chosen technological solutions should be safe, reliable and economical feasible. This further complicates the Marine Power System under development. It often requires a solution that involves multiple energy storage and conversion subsystems, and a proper integration, verification and validation of these subsystems into the complete Marine Power System.

It is in this light, that from ongoing developments in the sector MARIN experienced that a successful development of today's and tomorrow's Marine Power Systems require an integrated development method. MARIN has been working on the application of such a method, where the complete chain from user need analysis up till design verification can be done. Part of this chain is their Zero Emission Lab (ZEL). This lab consists of a range of energy suppliers and consumers connected to a 700 V DC bus, where all components are controlled by a dedicated power and energy management system. Per subsystem the maximum power is around 50 kW, where through scaling factors a real maritime Power Propulsion and Energy (PPE) system can be represented. Besides physical components (ZEL) also simulated components (virtual ZEL) can be included in verifications and validations.

In this 'lessons learned' paper MARIN will explain the motivation on why this lab was built, how it was built, and how the design, development and validation was linked to mentioned integrated methodology. Experienced complications showing up during development are shared and explained. Attention goes to how the chosen development method reduced the number of integration issues, how it strongly helped in early detection of problems and how it can support upcoming developments in the maritime sector.

Keywords: *Zero emission, Energy transition, Marine Power Systems, multi-disciplinary, DC, MBSE*

1. Introduction - motivation for building the engine room of the future

The Zero Emission Lab was established with a clear mission: to support the maritime sector in its transition towards sustainability[1]. Recognizing the urgent need for sustainable practices, MARIN initiated a facility dedicated to supporting this goal. This was all based on the idea to develop the engine room of the future, on a scaled level.

The goal in mind for the ZEL was that it should serve as an advanced lab, providing a cooperative test facility, supporting education, and creating a vast range of knowledge and experience. Although there are other integrated testing facilities, there is room for more variants and unique approaches[2], [3]. Besides the physical lab, at MARIN also a virtual version, v-ZEL, is envisioned, which can be run stand-alone or (partly) combined with the physical ZEL.

Since sustainability links with a lot of maritime aspects, the idea is that the ZEL should not only be able to address greenhouse gas and pollutant reduction, but also support in compliance with legislation and reliability, availability, (mission) performance, and cost efficiency aspects of future marine power systems in a multitude of configurational options. By focusing on these areas, the ZEL aims to meet the evolving needs and requirements of customers.

Knowledge and Experience: Both development and usage of the lab should result in a strong growth of experience in technology, integration, and development methodology. The goal is that MARIN can support

partners to navigate the complexities of sustainable future power systems, from regulatory compliance to optimizing performance and reducing costs.

Test Facility: An integrated lab facility could enable rigorous testing and validation of new technologies and practices. This goes both for hardware and software, and should ensure that innovations are not only effective but also reliable and compliant with current and future regulations.

Education: The ZEL can offer extensive educational possibilities for professionals and students with the skills and knowledge needed to drive today's and future technologies in the maritime sector. Through hands-on training and theoretical learning, it educates today's professionals and prepares the next generation of maritime experts.

Upcoming technologies, albeit new fuels, electric drives, DC architectures or advanced control algorithms, require continuous learning and are always open to new developments and perspectives. MARIN's laboratory has to be a place where cooperation and collaboration are key. The ZEL should actively seek feedback and foster an environment where partners can contribute to and benefit from shared knowledge.

During the development of the ZEL, the focus and emphasis changed. Where initially a large role was foreseen for component testing and validation, attention moved more and more to integration of (sub)systems and applying a suitable integrated development method. Although the lab is used for research and testing of individual parts and sub-systems, most attention goes to the application of the complete Power Propulsion and Energy (PPE) system in a maritime use-case.

This paper takes you through the process of the development of the ZEL. This starts in chapter 2 with an explanation of the ideas behind it, followed by the development process in chapter 3. The most important lessons learned during the development are discussed in chapter 4.

Figure 1-1 Overview of the ZEL, with on the far left the cavitation tunnel, in orange the Genset, cabinets with DC bus, with supercaps, and on the right the fuel cell.

2. Defining the goals

2.1. Stakeholders

Before detailing out the building of the ZEL, it is good to be aware of the stakeholders. In the following section they are listed, including their reason and relevance.

MARIN

MARIN is committed to strengthen its knowledge position within the industry on the topic of PPE systems and its

innovations. By building up expertise and resources, we aim to become a leading authority, driving innovation and best practices.

Maritime industry

Ship builders, owners and operators all have to deal with new technologies and new requirements for their ships. In some cases a need for knowledge and support is recognized upfront, in other cases this evolves once complications arise during design, building or operation of advanced PPE systems. This is where MARIN wants to support, and where the ZEL plays an important role.

Government, Regulating bodies

The government and entities involved in rules, regulations and legislation are a stakeholder since they require accurate information and insights in future sustainable PPE systems. The ZEL can support them in gaining these insights, to come to realistic and controllable goals and regulatory frameworks.

Academia, training and education

The academic and educational world needs access to up-to-date knowledge and state-of-the-art training facilities. MARIN is committed to bridging this gap by offering cutting-edge training and research resources, for future maritime professionals. Additionally, it is clear that companies also require ongoing training to keep up with new technological developments, and the ZEL is a place to meet that need. Both land-based and sailing employees benefit from gaining experience in the operation of future PPE systems.

2.2. User needs and requirements

Based on MARIN goals and roles of the stakeholder, the user needs for the laboratory were defined. The primary objectives include validating simulation (v-ZEL) models, providing education and training for ship crews and students, physically demonstrating v-ZEL results, and serving as a test facility for components and algorithms. Additionally, secondary goals encompass knowledge development, human-in-the-loop testing, configurability for various setups, combining ZEL and v-ZEL, performing PPE system tests, demonstrating compliance with safety regulations, conducting hardware and software-in-the-loop tests for customers, showcasing system integration aspects and user experience of future PPE systems, and executing (sub)-system performance and endurance tests.

As development progressed, the focus shifted from R&D to integration, revealing the complexity and unexpected challenges associated with this phase. This shift underscored the added value of the ZEL in demonstrating, explaining, and convincing stakeholders of the complex nature of future PPE systems, which often involve multiple power sources and consumers connected through advanced control mechanisms. It became evident that this integrated approach necessitates a dedicated methodology, appropriate tools, and extensive communication with experts.

After knowing the user needs on a generic level, a more discrete list of requirements could be defined. These are the starting point for the design phase, and are used for verification of both the design and the actual build. The requirements analysis resulted in the following list of properties to represent a future Marine Power System:

- Multiple energy suppliers
- Multiple energy storages
- Multiple energy convertors
- Multiple energy consumers
- Configurable control and automation
- DC primary distribution
- AC secondary distribution
- Cooling systems included
- Maritime building style
- Useable as training facility
- Configurable user interfacing
- Datalogging and data analysis capabilities

- Model based software development
- Software in the loop (virtual ZEL) capabilities

What was learned in this phase is that all stakeholders had to be involved to come to a complete overview, and that all requirements should be identified and recorded with enough detail. In this phase several talks with suppliers took place. Sometimes suppliers were hesitant to share information, which can be understood from a commercial point of view. As a downside it could happen that it was very hard to determine that their off the shelf solution was not suitable for our engine room of the future configuration. Here a very detailed description of specifications, requirements, interfaces and boundaries was needed, to come to the right solution. Only in this way proper system integration was possible. For MARIN it was relevant to be constantly aware of its role, which is not as a component developer, but as an assistant for system integration.

3. Development

3.1. Logical architecture

The system is designed around a central DC distribution system, which serves as the backbone for connecting both suppliers and consumers. One of the fundamental ideas behind the Zero Emissions Lab was this transition from an AC main grid to a DC grid, as many new components like fuel cells, batteries, and super capacitors operate on DC current. The centralized approach ensures efficient power distribution and management, allowing for seamless integration of various power sources and loads. In this way a direct connection, both physical and on a control level, between supplier and consumer is not required. Therefore, applying distributed droop control is suitable for this design.

By utilizing a DC distribution system, the design minimizes energy losses and enhances the overall reliability and stability of the power network. This configuration is particularly advantageous in applications where multiple power sources, such as renewable energy systems, and diverse consumers, need to be interconnected[4]. The central DC distribution system also facilitates easier scalability and adaptability, enabling the system to accommodate future expansions and technological advancements. Overall, this design approach provides a robust and flexible framework for managing complex power distribution needs.

Figure 3-1 Overview of the logical architecture of the ZEL.

All systems are built as intelligent building blocks, each with their own local controls. The building blocks that supply energy to the DC grid, to power the engine room of the future, are shown in Table 3-1. They should be able

to acts on their own in normal as well as in abnormal operational conditions, without detailed control from the central control system. The central control system only parametrizes the systems, to achieve the desired cooperation of the all active systems.

Table 3-1 Energy suppliers connected to the DC grid

<i>Technology</i>	<i>Energy source</i>
ICE - variable speed generator set	Fuel tank
Supercapacitor system	DC grid
Generic power system	MARIN AC grid
Battery system	DC grid
Fuel cell system	Compressed hydrogen
Grid Convertor System	DC grid
Electric Shaft Machine	DC grid

All depicted systems in Figure 3-1, the logical architecture, can be included or excluded in the configuration that actually will be tested. The actual configuration will be used to power the shaft-line in the ZEL. This shaft-line ends with a propeller in the MARIN cavitation tunnel, which represents the basic hydrodynamic resistance of a ship.

To represent electric propulsion, the shaft-line contains an electric shaft machine that can work both as power take-in and power take out. For mechanical or hybrid propulsion another electric motor is coupled, which represents the main propulsion engine of a ship. Initially here an actual Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) was foreseen. New insights, practical limitations, and the need to simulate a wide range of engine types made that this idea was replaced by implementing an electric ICE emulation motor. The energy to power this main engine emulator is not taken from the DC grid, since on the real ship this energy would come from the fuel tank and thus falls outside the system boundaries of the ZEL. For this reason, it is powered by the external MARIN AC grid.

Another electric machine in the shaft-line can be used to add disturbances that cannot be represented by the cavitation tunnel. For this the so called XMF electric machine is used. The power applied on this machine is calculated according to MARIN's eXtensible Modelling Framework (XMF). This contains a hydrodynamic model of the actual ship under realistic wave conditions and disturbances, used to add dynamics higher than can be implied by the ZEL propeller in the cavitation tunnel. Since on the real ship these disturbances are external, they are not powered from the ZEL DC grid, but from the external MARIN grid too.

Next to the propulsion power, the payload and auxiliary power consumers of a ship are represented in the ZEL. For this a secondary power distribution system was included in the logical architecture. Whether this would be an AC or DC grid was initially not decided. The connected consumers can be simulated or physically hooked up to the ZEL. In case of simulation, the consumed power is brought outside of the system boundaries towards the MARIN external AC grid to have a correct representation of the real ship. The secondary power distribution is also used to supply the power to the cooling systems in order to mimic a ship design.

The design of the ZEL automation and control system is based on the control hierarchy as shown in Figure 3-2. In this architecture, the zero control level is controlling the hardware of components in subsystems, while the subsystem itself is handled by the primary control level. Commanding the subsystems is done on the secondary control level, while balancing all systems (e.g. EMS and PMS) is done on the Tertiary control level. The management of the mission or operation is done in the quaternary control level, which for maritime cases can be divided between a shore based and a vessel based part.

The architecture is chosen such, that a combination between the physical ZEL and the virtual ZEL can be made in any chosen form. Simulations can be performed made where all components run as physical components in the ZEL, where virtual components are added or replacing virtual components from v-ZEL, or fully as a virtual model in v-ZEL. Adding remote components in other laboratories, via a Linked-Lab configuration, is initiated but not finalized yet.

Figure 3-2 Control hierarchy of the MARIN ZEL

3.2. Physical architecture

After finalizing the logical architecture, the development of the physical lab could be started. This started with an investigation on which power systems to include, based on the options in Table 3-1. Because of availability, market interest, rules and regulations, and simulation needs, the hardware shown in Table 3-2 was implemented.

Table 3-2 Implemented power systems in the ZEL

System	Size	Brand & type
ICE - variable speed generator set	55 kW	Abato Hatz 4H50TICD
Supercapacitor system	2x2000 kJ	AEP
Generic power system	63 kVA	Schmidbauer / Aradex
Fuel cell system	40 kW	Nedstack MT-FCPP40
Grid Converter system	43 kVA	Schmidbauer / Aradex
Electric Shaft Machine	83.8 kW	CEDS / FHSDPA-1025.08287.00

An overall view of the physical architecture is given in Figure 3-3. The main components will be further explained in the following paragraphs.

Figure 3-3 Physical architecture of the ZEL - single line representation.

3.2.1. Variable Speed ICE Generator system

MARIN intended to use a dual fuel methanol/diesel ICE. However in the power range up to 50 / 100 kW there are no DF ICE's on the market. MARIN opted for a Hatz diesel engine instead for the generator system. To contribute to the idea of zero emissions, MARIN decided to use HVO as fuel. To achieve the dual fuel methanol goal, a separate trajectory in cooperation with the HAN university of applied sciences was started to develop a dual fuel ICE conversion [5].

Classically a maritime genset is run at either 1500 rpm of 1800 to power a 50 or 60 Hz AC grid. In the ZEL case the genset runs at variable speed [6] and the produced AC electricity is converted into 700 V DC by an Aradex AC-DC converter. The speed setpoint is calculated by a MARIN control algorithm. Based on engine characteristics, it selects an engine speed where it can deliver the requested engine power at 70 to 80% of its load-capacity. This results in a good efficiency, and some room for fast power increases. To prevent too nervous engine behavior, the algorithm uses a very slow filter on the speed setpoint. Only when a situation could result in a lack of delivered power, the speed-setpoint can be updated fast. Next to the normal control data exchange some extra parameters of the ECU for engine monitoring purposes were added to the data-logging of this system.

After commissioning of the genset in the ZEL, it is not foreseen that on short term the methanol converted engine will be transferred from HAN to MARIN. For this reason a student project is started up to connect a dual fuel engine in a second genset in Arnhem to the ZEL and operate as a Linked Lab.

Figure 3-4 Variable Speed Generator Set

Table 3-3 Variable Speed Generator Set

<i>Detailed specs of the variable speed generator set</i>	
ICE	Hatz 4H50TICD 4 cylinder, 1952cc, EGR, DPF
Generator	Aradex VM600M-18W0073-RH20065-021B
AC DC converter	Aradex VP600-18W140-HP
Power @ rpm	55 kW @ 2800 rpm
Torque @ rpm	240 Nm @ [1500-2100] rpm
Peak fuel efficiency	40 %

3.2.2. PEM fuel cell system.

One of the challenges related to fuel cell is their design philosophy. Is it meant to be part of an AC grid system or DC grid system? The fuel cell contains an air blower to provide air to the stacks. This air blower is a large consumer of electricity. When the fuel cell is configured to deliver an AC current, this can also be used to supply the air blower. When the fuel cell is configured to deliver a DC current, either a DC-AC converter has to be added to the fuel cell system or the fuel cell system gets the balance of plant power from the AC support grid. This kind of detail is hard to find in the basic design information which is supplied by fuel cell suppliers, but is essential to build your electrical systems. MARIN did send a RFQ based on a FDTR for the fuel cell system to several well-known fuel cell suppliers but got hardly responses. Finally, MARIN bought the Nedstack fuel cell which was used in FELMAR [7], a project to develop and approve a marinized fuel cell.

In order to integrate the fuel cell in the ZEL, the same control design philosophy was adapted and a local system controller was developed. The local system controller controls the Fuel Cell as a system but sends the current set point directly to the DC/DC converter. Next to the normal control data exchange, some extra parameters of the stacks for monitoring purposes were added to the data-logging of this system. The implemented fuel cell has a need of an AC support grid for the Balance of Plant, of which the air blower is the major consumer. Nowadays, we recognize an increase in the application of DC components in fuel cells as a trend.

Table 3-4 Fuel Cell system

<i>Key specifications of the Fuel Cell</i>	
Fuel Cell	MT-FCPI-40
Stack model	LT-PEM 4 x Nedstack FCS13-XXL
System Peak power (BoL)	48 kWe
Stack Rated power (BoL)	55 KWe
Stack Voltage range	175 ... 350 V DC
Stack Current range	0 ... 230 A
System Nominal power	40 kWe
System Nominal Voltage	700 V DC
System Nominal Current	60 A

Figure 3-5 Fuel Cell system

3.2.3. Supercapacitor system

MARIN has installed two supercapacitor systems, make AEP, with a usable energy range of 2000 kJ. They are connected through Aradex DC-DC converters to the 700 V DC grid. The super capacitor system is fitted with a discharge unit for maintenance purposes.

The super capacitors are used either to

- Absorb high frequency power fluctuations in the DC distribution system
- Power payload systems which require a short, high energy burst of electrical power.
- Simulate a small battery

Table 3-5 Super Capacitor system

Key specifications of a Super Capacitor System	
Super Capacitors Make	AEP Products
Module type	LSUC 002R7C 3000F NH
Nominal Voltage	648 V DC
Nominal Cell Voltage	2.7 V
Cell Capacity	3000 F
Construction	5 modules of 48 cells
Operational Voltage range	200 - 600 V DC
Operational Voltage	450 V DC
Maximum Cell Current	+/- 350 A
System Nominal Energy range	- 1000 ... + 1000 kJ
System Peak Power	105 kW
System Nominal Voltage	700 V DC
System Peak Current	+/- 150 A

Figure 3-6 Super capacitor system

3.2.4. 700 V DC grid.

The ZEL DC architecture differs from a usual DC setup in the sense that converters are not integrated in the distribution panel but are part of the system which requires the converter. This is a different design approach and not many suppliers of DC systems have adopted this yet. Also tools to design such a system and perform calculations on, for instance, short circuit behavior are not readily available. MARIN had to develop their own simulation model and approach for this purpose. However, recent study [8] performed by TUDelft in the MENENS project shows benefits for this architecture. The architecture is shown Figure 3-7 and specified in Table 3-6.

The bus consists of two separate parts, a port side and starboard section. By means of a solid state circuit breaker they can be coupled or separated. On each side eight systems can be connected, each connection has its own power switch, fuses and current monitoring. Both sides of the distribution system have insulation monitoring and overvoltage protection which will be activated above 816 V DC.

Figure 3-7 700 V DC Main Distribution system.

Table 3-6 700V DC grid

Key specifications of 700 V DC grid	
Lower voltage	610 V DC
Nominal Voltage Range	640 ... 770 V DC
Upper voltage	800 V DC
Overvoltage protection Break Choppers	816 V DC
Overvoltage protection converters	KIMO TRANSOMIK BC2
Maximum current	200 A
Rail braker switch	Astrol DCB-IT-1000-200-A-003
Basis bus capacity	0 mF
Added bus capacity	2x 6 mF

3.2.5. 400 V AC grid

The 400 V AC grid is used to power the cooling system pumps and to deliver the auxiliary power to the fuel cell. The grid is built redundant, with a port side and a starboard section. The two sections, as shown in Figure 3-8, are connected through a bus tie, which is controlled by a Grid Measurement, Synchronization and Protection Module.

The 400 V AC grid can be powered directly from the MARIN 400 V AC grid or by the Grid converters. When the 400 V AC grid is powered from the MARIN grid, the pumps can be started before the rest of the ZEL is started. This was made possible to test the different systems without having to start all components like the generic converters and grid converters. However, in order to be able to test a ship's black start, the possibility to start up without a connection to the MARIN grid is on the wish list and will be worked out in the near future. The installed hardware already allows for this feature, but the required software still needs to be developed. Another feature identified later in the realization phase of the ZEL was the wish for extra power outlets. These are added to this grid in order to be able to connect additional power consumers and study the effects of power steps to the system. The key specifications of the 400V AC grid are listed in Table 3-7.

Figure 3-8 400 V AC Secondary Distribution system.

Table 3-7 The 400 V AC System

Key specifications of 400 V AC grid	
Nominal Voltage	400 V AC / 50 Hz
Maximum current	100 A
Grid measurement, synchronization and protection module	Bachmann GSP274
Connection to MARIN power grid	1x

3.2.6. Grid converter system

The grid converters are used to feed the 400 V AC grid from the 700 V DC grid. They consist of Aradex DC-AC converters and in the AC circuit an isolating transformer with LC-Filter and a CM-filter (make Schmidbauer).

The Aradex DC – AC converter can only provide a clockwise rotating grid whereas MARIN operated on an anti-clockwise rotating grid. As common practice, by changing the connection of two conductors this could be solved. However, as this issue was not identified at the start it caused much misunderstanding of the problems which occurred.

It is a redundant system with a grid converter connected to each side of the 700 V DC grid and the 400 V AC grid.

Figure 3-9 Grid converter

3.2.7. Generic converter – shore power

Initially the foreseen function of this system was to provide DC power to the DC bus from the MARIN AC grid, comparable to a shore connection for a ship. Later on it was decided to enhance this functionality and rename the system to Generic Converter System. In the enhanced functionality the system is used with a model in the loop, mimicking all kinds of (virtual) systems, or act as an extra load on the DC grid. Typically the Generic Converter will exchange power with the DC distribution grid based on real time control by v-ZEL systems.

The Generic Converter System is built up as a so-called Active Front End (AFE). The AC side is equipped with common mode and differential mode filtering. Galvanic isolation is in place by means of a transformer.

Figure 3-10 Generic Converter

3.2.8. Propulsion system

The Propulsion system consists of a combination of 3 electric motors. In order from left to right, see Figure 3-11. Their properties are listed in Table 3-8.

2100 XMF, Extensible Modelling Framework
 2300 ESM, Electric Shaft Machine
 2400 Main ICE, Internal Combustion Engine

Imposes external hydrodynamic behavior onto shaft
 Act as electrical shaft motor or generator
 Act as direct drive internal combustion motor

Figure 3-11 Propulsion system

The electric motors 2300 ESM and 2400 ICE can be independently connected to the shaft with clutches, according to the use or test set up at hand. The propulsion system is controlled using a virtual drive train model. This model contains all the inertia of the drive train (electric shaft machines, clutches, shafts and propeller) and simulation model of the ICE. It also incorporates the inertia of the drive train in the ZEL and accounts for the differences. This way we can adapt the propulsion system to different ship types.

Table 3-8 Propulsion system of the ZEL

Key specifications of Propulsion system			
motor	2100 XMF	2300 M/G	2400 ICE motor
Rated power	41.9 kW	83.7 kW	115 kW
Rated Torque	200 Nm	400 Nm	550 Nm
Rated Speed	2000 RPM	2000 RPM	2000 RPM
Type	CEDS FSDPA- 0921.08252.00	CEDS FHSDPA- 1025.08287.00	CEDS FSDPA- 1035.08293.00
Propeller	Exchangeable		

The propeller will dissipate the scaled power in the provided flow of water (up to 10 m/s) of the MARIN cavitation tunnel [9] in which it is mounted. 1. The Cavitation Tunnel acts as a quasi-static 50 kW propulsion load bank and as a visual and audio demonstrator of the working of the propeller; the latter especially when cavitation occurs. Although simulations up till 42kW could be performed with only the XMF motor, in practice the cavitation tunnel

is always connected because of its added demonstration value. The other way around the ZEL can also act as a modern well-controllable power source for the cavitation tunnel, which is now reviving for propeller research activities.

3.2.9. Automation and ICT

The physical implementation is based on the architecture as shown in Figure 3-2. The zero, primary and lower part of the secondary control layers are placed as close as possible to the systems. Most systems have their own Local System Control PLC (LSC). The upper part of the secondary and tertiary layer are implemented in the main control system. MARIN selected Bachmann technology for this system because of its common use in maritime applications. Also Bachmann has the possibility to integrate MATLAB/Simulink functions in the control. This made it possible to use ‘model-in-the-loop’[10] simulation or implement controllers based on Simulink in the PLCs.

The system architecture is a redundant design on most aspects. MARIN adopted a warm-redundant system, ensuring that a master PLC is always active to be able to control the lower and upper automation layers. A separate safety system is in place, also Bachman. The safety philosophy is to comply to the local machine safety directive and varies slightly from an on board situation.

Figure 3-12 Control room of the ZEL during a demonstration.

The on board situation can be mimicked and experienced by standing in the ZEL control room, where the operator interfaces are and from where the PPE system under test can be controlled, also via levers and steering equipment. The control room, as shown in Figure 3-12, is located such that overview over the physical ZEL is available.

4. Discussion - Lessons learned

4.1. External positioning of the ZEL and its development

Although the goal for which MARIN started the ZEL development never changed, its actual role slightly moved during the development process. Where it was initially foreseen to mainly use it as a modular testing facility for systems from external suppliers, in the end most interest goes to using it for integration, concept validation, sizing questions, control&automation system development and training & education. These are the type of projects that are currently deployed at the ZEL. At the same time it was recognized that it required extensive explanation to have the complexity of a future marine power system and its development understood. This goes hand in hand with the awareness that an integrated development method is essential to overcome all integration challenges upfront. When this is not done with enough attention, problems will show up during commissioning or operation. For the ZEL this happened to a minor extend, which was accepted as being a learning experience. When this happens on the real ship, it will be dangerous and extremely costly. Looking at the scale on which commissioning problems occur on today's ships with traditional powering [11], it is without any discussion that this has to be prevented for future ships with more complex power systems. The ZEL development showed that a suitable way of working, integrated system development and proper documentation are essential.

More than in traditional technology development projects it was learned that cooperating effectively with external suppliers requires clear communication and precise definition of system boundaries. It showed to be essential to specify what is included in a system and what is not, to avoid misunderstandings. Since many solutions and approaches in the ZEL are new, suppliers often are not aware of it and may offer standard products that do not meet the specific needs. It showed to be essential to communicate with experts, ask detailed questions, and ensure all requirements are identified and recorded with sufficient detail. In this way creating a common understanding helps in aligning expectations and achieving successful collaboration.

4.2. Way of working

4.2.1. Composition and working method of the team.

The ZEL covers a wide knowledge area, which required a multi-disciplinary team to develop and validate it. This team has been built up with the needed experts during the development of the ZEL, and includes electrical, system, control, automation, mechanical, maritime, and engine specialists. A quality that was required for all experts is an analytical way of working, both for development and for troubleshooting. It turned out to be beneficial to have some overlap in knowledge areas over the team-members. Not only did this improve the speed of content development, but it also enabled peer reviewing within the team.

Having a common goal made the group of experts, which were sourced both from within and outside of MARIN, a strongly connected team. Multiple approaches were tried to make this team work as effective as possible, where agile scrum [12] proved to be the most beneficial. A sprint length of three weeks was applied, consisting of four sprint days per week. This helped to focus on each ZEL development topic for a significant amount of time, and reduced content-switching. During the development it was noticed that content switching strongly decelerated the pace of the ZEL development. When agile scrum is followed it still requires attention to limit the number of goals per sprint. Because of diversity of the team, stakeholder-pressure and practical limitations and opportunities, this was not always easy to stick to.

4.2.2. Finish things.

Engineers are always interested in new challenges ahead, and stakeholders often have the tendency to bring their new wishes and requirements to the table as soon as they arise. Although the scrum way of working already intends to prevent ad-hoc activities, often for a new sprint completely new developments are prioritized. In this way the capabilities of the laboratory are continuously extended and new projects can be served fast. During the development of the ZEL it became clear that this approach also has a severe disadvantage. The focus on new development comes at the cost of unfinished ongoing work. An important lesson learned is that this is something that should be prevented. Since often the devil is in the details, it is commonly very hard to predict how much time is needed for the complete finalization of developments. The resulting under-estimation worsens this issue. It was recognized in multiple working fields.

This aspect played a role when balancing requirements engineering versus the actual building. Since it is very time consuming to get all detailed insights from all stakeholders, requirements are not easily finalized. This made it tempting to start with developments once the dominant requirements became clear. This happened for example with the cooling system. After having the complete system-overview ready and all requirements collected, this resulted multiple times in a need for modifications on the just built equipment. This takes extra time and costs, which could have been prevented when the requirements phase was completely finished before starting to build.

The development of PLC software often takes multiple iterations. Once the basic functionality is developed and verified, basic operations could be performed in the lab. This often happened, to be able to do the first simple proof of concept tests. As a consequence the priority of finishing the software development reduced. This resulted in doing a part of the work with unfinished software, in which known errors and omission kept on coming back. Overall this led to a stronger reduction of development speed than the quick start added to it. The lesson learned here is that only 100% ready PLC software should be committed, and it should only be taken into use once fully validated against requirements. This implies that requirements are important and necessary in an early phase, with as much detail as possible. While often this is found to be too elaborate and not in place upfront.

Both because of unfinished tasks and because of unexpected behavior of components and/or subsystems problems can show up during operation. Most engineers are usually very good at inventing work-arounds to finish ongoing activities. During the development of the ZEL it was recognized that nevertheless, enough priority should be given to completely solving such issues. An example was again the cooling system. Initially this had some problems, which quite regularly resulted in a shutdown of the lab. After this happened multiple times, it was decided to take a dedicated period of time to work on all these issues. During this period the lab could not run, but in the end it showed to be more effective since it prevented further downtime.

4.2.3. Integrated way of working

The ZEL is a complex system. This means that for its development a working method should be used that can handle this complexity and is able to connect all different steps in the development process. Because of this required integrated way of working, attention was drawn towards model based tools and methods. MARIN had only limited experience in methods for complex systems so an investigation was needed for this. As a first step model based tools from system engineering and automation were investigated, to develop the system architecture and controls. Through a course using Sparx Enterprise Architect as software tool it proved that sysML was to be too difficult: sysML has so many options to build a model but is lacking a straightforward approach for system modeling.

Figure 4-1 Arcadia method for Model Based System Engineering

MARIN has been looking for a Model Based System Engineering (MBSE) method standing more close to the engineering practice than SysML. A pathway is needed for system modelling and, MARIN came across a method called Arcadia [13], developed by Thales. It defines a clear method to do system modelling in four discrete steps, depicted in Figure 4-1. Thales developed an open source tool named Capella [14] to do this. Capella was adopted by MARIN to model the system and this is used as input for control software development for the ZEL.

Although this approach was solid, it did not always work out that way. Main reason for this was the time required to learn to work with Capella and actually build the model. This clearly showed up by the outsourced software development for the ZEL control PLCs. Having not yet finished the Software Design Specification originating from the MBSE

model, development was already started based on own ideas and assumptions. As a result, multiple iterations and corrections were needed to come to the required functionalities. The same happened with calculation results already used for the design, or designs made by suppliers, before the MBSE model of the ZEL was completed.

During the outsourcing phase we also have tried to use our MBSE approach to obtain comparable quotes for systems, as the fuel cell and the batteries, from different suppliers. These systems are more complex and typically not an “off the shelf” product. We made a FDTR (Functional Description and Technical Requirements) describing what we (the ZEL) needed of the system to do. This enables a supplier to offer the best solution in their scope, understanding how their system would be used. It appeared that not all suppliers were able to follow this line of thinking and kept offering a standard product. A conclusion is that to build a complex system, the system integration is an important role that often will remain with the client.

4.2.4. Documentation

A complex system, developed by a dynamic team of engineers, requires good documentation. It promotes fact based discussion and communication on technical issues and solutions. Good documentation should make clear what the requirements of a (sub-)system are, and what its boundaries and inputs and outputs are. It is preferred to have documentation which acts as a single source of truth. This prevents that various people are working with different documentation, especially in case of modifications (both for the real system, as for the documentation).

Part of documentation for the ZEL development was the implementation of a system numbering structure, the Product Data List. Because the systems are getting more and more complex, and the same component can occur multiple times onboard, in different applications, a uniform numbering helps in preventing misunderstanding. An overview and example of the structure is shown in Figure 4-2.

Figure 4-2 Product data list structure -fuel cell example

The system worked well during the development of the ZEL. Room for improvement can be found in the strictness of prescribing this structure to suppliers. During our project that was not done with all suppliers, which made it practically impossible to relate external developed parts of the PLC code to subsystems. In cases where this relation could still be made afterwards, this showed to be very time consuming. In cases where both customer and supplier used the same structure, it showed to be highly beneficial.

Not only to support the Arcadia working method, but also for documentation, Capella was used as a tool. It should serve as a single source of truth, containing not only documentation of individual parts and (sub) system, but also their relation and their connection with requirements and design choices made in the project. It showed to be a strong advantage to have single source of truth, and to be able to trace back design choices to their requirements. Nevertheless it showed to be cumbersome to have the complete team adopt Capella model for all documentation. Multiple causes were experienced during the implementation of Capella in the ZEL development team:

- The tool requires a significant amount of training time
- Complex to use
- Making updates is time consuming and prone to errors
- Possibilities for cooperation are limited
- Time required to visualize models properly limits usage for communication
- Little attention for definition of requirements.

Because of listed reasons, also other methods for documentation were used, mainly document based. Often this was related to the implementation of changes, because of unforeseen component behavior, new insights, added requirements, etc. The newly created situation could theoretically be put in the system design (the Capella Model). Instead, measurements, motivations, side effects, and detailed data and actions often were noted in reports on the project drive, in One-note or Outlook. This disrupts the single source of truth approach and thus creates confusion. On the other hand it often ensured information that would otherwise have been lost, and regularly helped to make the documentation clear and easily accessible. A clear lesson learned is that a uniform way to track changes is preferred, and that updating schemes, diagrams and architectures is essential.

What in the end the best tool for documentation is, is to be decided. After more training and streamlining of the tool setup, Capella could be an option. Comparable model based tools are to be considered. When a document-based approach is chosen, much emphasis has to be placed on the structure, versioning and document-management. The main take-away from this development project is that documentation should be unambiguous, clear, up-to-date, helpful in communicating information and supporting cooperation.

4.3. Technology implementations

4.3.1. Energy sources

LNG

One of the most dominant changes for future shipping compared to today's diesel fuel oil dominated powering, will be the energy sources applied. The initial design was based on the idea that LNG would become the new energy source for combustion engines in ships.

Interest in LNG significantly decreased however, since the recent insight on direct emissions of methane to the atmosphere during the processing of natural gas [15], which has, with its high Global Warming Potential, a significant contribution to global warming. MARIN changed the design from using methane to other energy sources like methanol and hydrogen.

Methanol

The purpose of methanol would be to apply it in a dual fuel combustion engine, which is not installed at the moment. As preparation a study was performed on what setup would be needed to do this and also a HAZID was performed. It was based on the IMO guidelines for using Methyl/Ethyl alcohols as fuel [16]. The methanol tank would be placed outside the building. Inside the building a double wall pipe with ventilation would be used to supply methanol to the engine. Also a Nitrogen system should be added to flush the methanol system after use and for servicing.

Hydrogen

For the fuel cell it was chosen to use compressed hydrogen storage. The compressed hydrogen storage and supply system consists of 4 bottle racks of 16 bottles each. The design pressure of the storage system is 300 bar, which is based on commercially available bottle racks. The details of the hydrogen storage and supply system are described in a separate section.

Batteries

It was intended to install a battery system in the ZEL. The battery system should be based on a lithium chemistry and represent a common used type in shipping. MARIN requested offers from several parties and they all suggested to use a Lithium Ferro Phosphate type battery.

From a MARIN market perspective the standards to be used should be based on maritime applications, for example from Classification or IMO. Class societies have already rules in place for the use of battery electric storage systems on board ships. MARIN performed a HAZID according to DNV class rules and made provisions to be able to install the battery to mitigate the risks identified in this study.

ZEL, however, is also a land-based laboratory and has to conform with national and EC regulations. When MARIN started the design of the ZEL there were no Dutch or EC regulations on the use of battery energy storage systems, only some provisional rules. Only by the end of 2023 a standard was published, the PGS 37-1. MARIN applied for a permit to use a battery system in the ZEL based on the provisional rules and received the permit. Two conditions proved to be very hard to fulfill for the moment:

Placing a battery electric storage system on a floor in a building requires:

- 1) The battery shall be tested according to the UL-9540A or EN-IEC 62933-5-2 protocol, and
- 2) The battery shall be placed in a watertight compartment, fillable with water by the fire brigade

The installation of a battery electric storage system is halted for the moment. However, the 700 V DC grid is fitted with two spare bays, suited for connecting a battery system in the future, when implementing is seen more realistic regarding the regulations.

A battery emulation system was investigated. Finally it was decided that the emulation of a battery system can be performed sufficiently by the Generic Systems or the Super Capacitor system. The benefit of having a separate battery emulation system was judged as relatively low. Renewed insights, market interest and reactions during demonstrations at the ZEL, made clear it is necessary to have physical batteries in the ZEL. The challenge will be to fit the battery system as a retro fit.

4.3.2. Compressed Hydrogen Storage

The hydrogen for the fuel cell is stored in racks with 16 bottles of 50 liters at 300 bar, placed outside of the building. Each bottle rack is connected to a hydrogen connection and safety blocks fitted with a solenoid valve to enable/block the flow to the gas control block.

With the design, and hardware, the procedures to operate the Storage System was delivered by Marine Services Noord. At that time MARIN had no experience in Hydrogen and knew that the system was not completely finished. The automation of the storage system was to be out sourced, so the knowledge behind the procedures had to be conveyed to software engineers and operators. Therefore details of the design were adjusted in hindsight during the commissioning phase.

Initially the system was designed with two thermal valves on each bottle rack to protect the bottle racks in case of an external fire. From the HAZID for this system it was concluded that the probability of an external fire at the location of the bottle racks was very small and therefore the thermal release valves were omitted. Instead, on that specific port of the gas connection and safety block, an extra vent valve was added connected to the vent, see Figure 4-3 (A). Through this vent valve the flexible hose between the bottle rack and the gas connection block can be purged during a bundle change. The bundle connection procedure was simplified by this change afterwards.

Figure 4-3 Condensed P&ID H₂ Storage – (A) Bundle Vent - (B) Pressure Reducer – (C) Venting – (D) Pressure Relief

The gas control block contains a single pressure regulator valve and a pressure relief valve, Figure 4-3 (B) and (D), to prevent high pressure in the hydrogen supply line. Using a single pressure regulator maximizes the amount of hydrogen which can be drawn from the storage system. The supplier intended to fit a Tescom 44-1300 pressure regulator, which has a very low decay inlet characteristic of 0.1 psi/100 psi pressure drop. Instead the installed regulator valve at MARIN has a decay of 1 psi/100 psi. This means that when the supply pressure drops, the outlet pressure increases. The effect is that over the whole operating range (from 300 to 5 barg supply) the outlet pressure rises above the limits of the pressure relief valve (7 bar). So, this valve opens and will vent excess hydrogen. This was not the intention of the design; the pressure relief valve should only come into action when the pressure regulator fails. A lessons learned here is that much more detail of the pressure regulator valve and the pressure relief valve had to be studied and taken into account when sizing this system.

Several normally closed solenoid valves of the hydrogen storage are internally fitted with a pilot valve that needs back pressure to close. When pressurizing the system with those valves closed, they still leak some high pressure gas. This is causing a high pressure behind the closed valve. The lesson is this is in line with the previous, one has to know on component level what to design, or from the process side, quote for the specific behavior of the sub-system one needs.

All vents, gas connection block, main vent valve and pressure relief valve, are connected to the vent stack, Figure 4-3 (C), to release the hydrogen if needed. The design and evaluation of the vent stack was subcontracted to Norwegian consultant HyEx, experienced in hydrogen systems. They made CFD calculations to find the extend of a burning hydrogen cloud, pressure levels and heat loads. One of the main issues in the engineering of the vent stack is the outlet velocity. In case this velocity is higher than the speed of sound blockage may occur in the vent stack leading to an explosion. Very high speeds also cause a very high sound pressure level. The diameter of the MARIN vent stack is designed for a maximum speed of about 200 m/s. An orifice in the vent lines is used to limit the flow rates and keep the velocity below this speed. The time needed to vent the content of the storage increases lightly but prevents worse effects. Here a tradeoff had to be made between different risks. The height of the vent stack above is 3 m above the roof.

Together with HyEx, MARIN did the HAZOP of the hydrogen storage and supply system. Hydrogen burns without a visible flame. In order to be able to detect a hydrogen flame MARIN installed special cameras which observe the hydrogen storage area and the fuel cell. An acoustic detection system which can detect hydrogen leakage was also advised but omitted because of the high price, long delivery time and advice from Nedstack about their operational experience with their hydrogen storage.

Because MARIN operates a facility on land a permit had to be acquired for the installation. MARIN used the PGS-35, Waterstofinstallaties voor het afleveren van waterstof aan voertuigen en werktuigen [17] to define the safety measures for their hydrogen storage and supply system. This standard is based on a risk based design approach and was very well suited to this purpose.

The procedures for operation of the Compressed Hydrogen System were reviewed by the ZEL team for commissioning of the Fuel Cell. By checking the process, several improvements were found. Meanwhile the safety system was already designed, and the procedures were already programmed in the PLC and approved by FAT testing. As a result, after every meeting the procedures and safety functionality had to be re-programmed and re-drawn. This took a long time. Lesson learned: use the following, correct, order:

- Review the procedures.
- Design functionality and Safety functions.
- Give order to programmer of functionality and safety functions.
- Validate the system and freeze the setup. If changes are necessary, use a change request.

4.3.3. Cooling system

MARIN opted to standardize the cooling systems as much as possible. All cooling skids for low temperature and medium temperature are made according to one design, only the capacity of the heat exchangers varies. The manifolds are also all made to one basic design detailed in 3 versions: DN15, DN32 and DN60. This standard design proved to be beneficial for clearness and development speed. However, it showed the disadvantage that potential problems now occur in all systems. This happened with an electrically controlled coolant flow valve, which showed a slow response, inaccuracy and an extremely high failure rate.

The cooling systems are fitted with frequency regulated pumps and each manifold can be controller individually to optimize cooling performance and minimize the power consumption of the cooling systems. Until now not much effort has been put into the optimization of these systems, there is still room for improvement.

In general, the cooling system is very important to the equipment. A cooling system error causes the units requiring cooling to block. Initially this happened often and each time took effort to fix, causing the ZEL being inoperable for a while. Soon it was concluded that it would be more effective to pause the operation of the ZEL for two weeks and fix all cooling problems once and forever.

MARIN envisaged to use a high temperature cooling system for the variable speed genset and the fuel cell. However, these systems have their own high temperature cooling systems installed. MARIN had to supply only raw water to these systems. For that reason, a high temperature cooling system was not implemented.

The ZEL contains a lot of water cooled electronics and motors. These operate at a temperature between 35 – 40 °C. Two medium temperature cooling systems are installed which can backup each other. In case of a failure still one medium temperature cooling system can stay running.

A low temperature system, which initially was intended for a water cooled battery system, is now used to cool the intercooler and the generator of the variable speed genset and the AC-DC converter for the genset. Typically, the converter would have been connected to the Medium temperature cooling system. For reason of not having sufficient MT cooling connections the LT cooling is used instead. This can be seen as an example of not having investigated all requirements sufficiently upfront. If this would have been done, the lack of a MT cooling connection would not have occurred. The layout of the complete system is shown in Figure 4-4.

Figure 4-4 Schematic representation of the ZEL cooling system

On board of ships a raw water cooling system supplies cooling capability for the other cooling systems. In the ZEL also raw water is used for this purpose, coming from the MARIN Concept Basin acting as a heat sink. When starting the cooling system it might take too long to reach an equilibrium because of the Raw cooling water low temperature. A three way control valve, also shown in Figure 4-4, is installed between the inlet and return of the RAW cooling system. This improved the warm up time and controllability of the system.

4.3.4. Electric

During commissioning of the ZEL, noise and disturbance were found during the operation of the converters. For smooth commissioning the switching frequency was reduced from the design value 8 kHz to 4 kHz. When detailed measurements were performed later on, it showed that while the DC bus voltage (between positive and negative DC pole) was stable, there were large variations in the voltage of the poles to earth. Figure 4-5 shows that the negative pole of the DC-bus had large voltage variations that reached 600 V. A model of the system was created in PSIM and simulation confirmed the source of the disturbance being common mode resonance.

Figure 4-5 Measurements on the DC-bus. C1 is the DC-bus voltage, C2 is the voltage between the negative pole and earth, and C3 is the voltage on the resistor in the common-mode filter. The negative pole had voltage variations of about 600 V.

Two solutions for this issue were investigated:

- Damping the resonance;
- Moving the resonance frequency to a point in the spectrum where it is harmless.

As the resonance frequency varied as more systems were connected to the grid, it was concluded that finding a suitable circuit for damping the resonance would be difficult. Therefore, the focus was to move the resonant frequency. This was achieved by increasing the converter switching frequency from 4 kHz to back to the design value 8 kHz and adding two 0.47 μF capacitors in the common mode path. Simulations showed that this would reduce the resonance frequency to ~ 2.4 kHz. This improvement was implemented and measurements showed that the voltage variation on the two poles was reduced to under 100 V.

The DC-Distribution system implemented in the ZEL has a distributed architecture, i.e., the converters are not integrated in the distribution panel, but are part of the system that uses it. This is a different design approach with its advantages [8], however, it has not yet been widely adopted.

The concept of overcurrent protection of the DC-Distribution system is based on fast acting fuses in the bays and a solid state circuit breaker between the port and starboard side of the distribution. Two sets of fuses were found necessary:

- one set in the bay for overload and short circuit protection against short-circuits in the cable and close-to or in the converter;
- one set in the pre-charge and main contactor assembly for short circuit protection only, as the converter close by performs overload control. This protects against short circuits in the DC bus.

Another challenge in the design of such distributed DC-Distribution systems was the lack of tools and knowledge for design, for example, the tools required for performing short-circuit calculations. Some of the challenges faced were:

- *Getting a complete protection design from a supplier.* Getting a full advise failed and the fuse selection was finally based on short circuit simulations performed.
- *Getting short-circuit simulations performed.* Initially, the simulations were outsourced, however, this proved to be not flexible enough for the development stage of the ZEL in general and the DC distribution in particular. Finally a model handling fast occurrences relevant for short circuit situations of the Main DC-Distribution and the connected systems in the power circuit simulation tool PSIM was developed in-house and the maximum expected short circuit current deduced.
- *Getting fuses with an acceptable lead time.*

- *Get fuses that fit in the distribution system hardware.*

This last two challenges made us change fuses a few times, where every change required rechecking whether the new found fuses fit the requirements.

While testing the 700 V DC bus droop control, it proved to be difficult to keep the voltage at the 700 V DC bus stable. There was a significant ripple on the 700 V. Two measures were taken:

- Faster bus voltage measurement was added to the droop control to decrease latency time.
- Extra capacitance was added to the bus. The Aradex converters have a relatively low DC capacitor compared to converters typically used for industrial drive systems. This leads to a relatively low DC capacitance connected to the DC distribution, especially when not all nodes are connected. Therefore 6 mF of capacity is added to each side of the DC bus. From a control engineering perspective: adding capacitance reduces the gain of the voltage control loop.

Adding capacitors influences the short circuit behavior of the DC grid. New short circuit simulations were performed in order to check whether the existing fuses still comply and to find suitable fuses the capacitor bay of the DC distribution.

In the initial DC distribution the design consisted of a distributed design, with breakers and fuses on the distribution side, to be connected with the individual energy suppliers and consumers. The energy suppliers and consumer would have their own converters to exchange the energy with the distribution net. At later stage it was realized that for each connection, current and voltage measurements were desired at the individual side of a unit, as well as connect and disconnect functionality. This resulted in an extra medium sized cabinet for each connecting unit to the distribution. This resulted in a challenging issue for space in the ZEL to fit those cabinets.

While operating the lab, an 8 kHz audible noise was observed from the Grid Converters. Further investigation observed beating with a variable beating frequency which did not change with the switching frequency of the converter. Measurements showed that there was a distortion on the phase voltage when the noise was audible. Spectral analysis showed a large third-harmonic component. The control settings of the system did not influence the noise, however, the AC frequency did influence. This led to the conclusion that it was the beating between the 50 Hz MARIN grid and the frequency generated by the grid converter. To find a solution, the simulation model of the ZEL electrical system was extended. Simulations showed that when two (or more) converters equipped with common mode filters are active, with anti-phase third harmonic injection, the common mode voltage of the AC voltages increases. This leads to higher currents through the common mode filter leading to the audible noise. Increasing the switching frequency to 16 Hz not only reduced the current but also moved the noise to the border of human hearing.

Conclusions

Sustainable shipping requires a complex range of technological solutions, which are realistically represented in MARIN's Zero Emission Laboratory.

A complex system requires a structured and integrated development approach. The perfect way of working was not found yet, but using Capella and the Arcadia - MBSE approach during the development was a useful step. For a number of design decisions it was better to have had this approach earlier in the development process.

The development of the MARIN Zero Emission Laboratory, showcasing relevant integration issues, appeared to be a useful way to support future marine power systems engineering.

Solid documentation showed to be essential during the development process. A significant amount of complications during the development process were related to shortcomings in documentation.

The added value of the ZEL showed to be not only in the technology of its components, but also in showing and experiencing the related system integration and interaction aspects.

Both during development and application, the combination of a physical lab (ZEL) and its virtual representation as simulation model (v-ZEL) showed to be highly beneficial. The simulations give more insights in the (expected) behavior of the real components, while the hardware was of strong support for control development.

MARIN is committed to support the industry, and to strengthen its own knowledge position on sustainable shipping. Both technological and methodological expertise, products and cooperations will be expanded to achieve this.

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